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Explaining the homosexual behavior of people and electrons at temperatures close to the absolute zero

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Abstract

In all living beings, the attraction between the sexes (males and females) is magnetic in origin, which means that the aura (Spirits) of the two sexes spin in opposite directions. This article explains that the homosexual behavior of people (who are attracted to the same gender) is caused by the presence of dark Spirits of the opposite gender, who make their aura (Spirit) to spin in direction opposite to their gender. The electrons normally pair with opposite spins, but at very low temperatures close to the absolute zero, when superconductivity is observed, the electrons were found to couple with parallel spin (called Cooper pairs). The “homosexual” behavior of the electrons has the following roots: at these extremely low temperatures the electrons don’t have energy to spin, and when they don’t spin, they are waves (spin = 0).

Key words: magnetic origin of gender attraction; why are homosexual homo-attracted; what causes their opposite spinning; why electrons couple with parallel spin; wave-particle duality.

1. Introduction – the Whole Material World Is Material Body and Field

The year 2025 was pronounced International Year of Quantum Science and Technology. If so, it is the about time to accept the fact that we (and everything material) have auras and since “Aura” means “Light” in Hebrew, and the light is in quants, the whole material world is material bodies and quantum halves. This is the basis of the dualism wave-particle, which comes from the way the material world was created [1], [2]. But how was the material world created?

All nonlinear electromagnetic fields (NEMF) do not dissipate and can imprint information. If so, NEMF is the perfect material to create a Universe. First a non-

dissipating Space Matrix NEMF was created, then on it was imprinted the information (the holographic tri-dimensional image of the Universe to be) and the Universe was created. Here are the details of it.

First, with rotational scooping of the Space Matrix NEMF, Black Holes of anti-matter were created. These Black Holes created the whole material world by sucking from one side of their holes the weak NEMF of the Space Matrix, increasing it 1,000 times with their fast spinning, and spitting from the other side (of their holes) material plasma balls (stars).

Thus, the material plasma balls (stars) had field $NEMF_m$, which was 1,000 times stronger than the field of the Space Matrix NEMF.

This made every material particle - a particle and wave at the same time, which is the basis of the duality wave-particle and explains why the particles sometimes behave like particles (photo effects) and sometimes like waves (diffraction).

2. The Creation of the Living Beings in the Material World and the Creation of the Gender

The next step was the creation of living beings to populate the material world. To give them unlimited number of creative ways to adapt and survive, to the material body (with its NEMFm) a living force NEMFs was magnetically attached. For this to happen, the living force NEMFs was made to spin in direction opposite to the spinning of the NEMFm of the material body.

NEMFs was created in the following way. On the weak Space Matrix NEMF information was imprinted, which made all living beings emotional and creative. Being a field, NEMFs had fast waves, which allowed:

1. all living beings to react fast and survive,
2. fast adaptation by scanning the new environment with its waves and sending signals to the material body how to change to adapt to the new environment, and
3. evolution to new species, when the new environment was drastically different.

Also, the living beings were made male and female.

1. The living force NEMFs of men was spinning clockwise and sucking energy from heaven through the top of their heads (from here came the concept of Father God in Heaven).
2. The living force NEMFs of women was spinning counterclockwise and sucking energy from Earth (from here came the concept of Mother Goddess of Earth).

Since the living force NEMFs of men and women spins in opposite direction, the attraction between the opposite sexes (male and female) is magnetic in origin [3].

Since the living force NEMFs of all living beings is magnetically attached to the NEMFm of the material body, when the material body is worn out and stop functioning, the living force NEMFs leaves. Then the person is pronounced clinically dead, and the material body becomes a good-for-nothing empty shell that need to be discarded.

3. Why Are the Homosexuals Attracted to the Same Gender?

To answer this question, I need to explain the origin of

the population on Earth. The Bible says that Nephilim mated with Earthly Women and this is how the Earth population originated. Since the Nephilim were different species (Reptilian), they had to genetically re-engineer the Earthly Women to be able to mate with them.

This explains: 1/ the presence of Reptilian brain in our head, and 2/ the fact that our material bodies can house both: white good Angelic Spirits and dark bad Reptilian Spirits. In my article [4], I explained that the people on Earth born with dominant negative thinking have dominant Nephilim genes.

We all have at least one dark Spirit, but some people have two or three. When the dark Spirits in a man are three and two of them are female, the aura spins like a female aura, the person feels like a female, and is attracted to another male. When the dark Spirits in a woman are three and two of them are male, she feels like a male, and is attracted to another female.

This means that all homosexuals have dominant Nephilim genes, which made them inborn negative thinkers. Being negative thinkers, they attracted negative dark Spirits, which feed with negative energy. However, only when two of 3 negative Spirits are the opposite gender, the person feels affinity to the same gender, i.e. he is homosexual.

4. Why Do Electrons Behave like Homosexual (Couple with Parallel Spin) at very Low Temperatures Close to the Absolute Zero?

Our scientists found that the electrons normally couple with opposite spin because by spinning in opposite direction they create opposite magnetic polarity, which is the basis of their attraction. However, at very low temperatures close to the absolute zero (-273 K), when superconductivity is observed, the electrons couple with parallel spin (called Cooper pairs) in the name of the scientist who first observed them [5].

Why does the electrons become homosexual (couple with parallel spins) at temperatures close to the absolute zero? As a Quantum scientist, in this Year of Quantum Science and Technology, I feel obligated to offer an explanation of the homosexual behavior of the electrons at very low temperatures [6]. I am going to explain why the Cooper pairs exist and what they mean.

Recent research found that at very low temperatures close to the absolute zero (-273 K), the particles behave like waves [7].

My explanation is – when the temperature is close to the absolute zero and the particles don't have energy to spin, they become waves [6]. And if the particles become waves, which do not spin, the spin does not matter anymore, and they form Cooper pairs.

5. Conclusion

Thus, the homosexual behavior of men and electrons have different origin.

1/ Men are homosexual (attracted to men) when their aura (Spirit) spins counterclockwise like female aura (Spirit). This is because they have three negative Spirits, and two of them are female Spirits, which makes them feel like a female.

2/ Women are homosexual (attracted to women) when their aura (Spirit) spins clockwise like men's aura. This is because they have three negative Spirits and two of them are male Spirits, which makes them feel like a male.

The electrons normally couple with opposite spin, but at very low temperatures close to the absolute zero (-273 K), they form Cooper pairs because at these very low temperatures [7], the electrons don't have energy to spin,

and when they don't spin, they are waves [6].

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